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Working from Home (WfH) environments to enhance well-being and productivity

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Abstract:

Purpose: We conducted a scoping online survey to answer these two research questions: What are the best solutions to space design for working from home (WfH) to enhance well-being and productivity? What changes to their home spaces have knowledge workers and public administrators in the East Midlands made to enable WfH during COVID-19 lockdown?

Approach: we surveyed knowledge workers and public administrators from the East Midland Region in 2021 with a total of 98 valid responses recruited through a combination of purposive and convenient sampling. The online survey was shared via Leicester-based employers: De Montfort University, Leicester City Council, and East Midlands chamber. We designed the survey to capture both qualitative and quantitative experiences. We analysed the survey using these methods: descriptive analysis, conceptual content analysis, and correlation analysis.

Key findings: our survey identified a dedicated workspace as a significant contributor to comfort and wellbeing while WfH. Surveyed employees prioritised environmental control, comfortable furnishings, and adequate space in WfH environments.

Implications: WfH is here to stay and it will need comprehensive considerations from both employees and employers to ensure that subjective well-being is integrated. Employee-centred environments design and solutions will enhance wellbeing and productivity.

Keywords: COVID-19 lockdown, knowledge workers, productivity, public administrators, well-being, and working from home (WfH) environments.

Main highlights:

- A dedicated workspace enhances well-being in WfH environments

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- Employees value environmental control, comfort, and adequate space when WfH
- Employee-centred design supports well-being and productivity
- WfH requires joint employer–employee design considerations customised to work activities.

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Introduction

Working from home (WfH) is increased post COVID-19 pandemic because of the global lived working experiences of employees. The Global Forum on Productivity proposed a set of policy actions strategy to support hybrid working (that is, working partly from home, and partly outside it) after the pandemic. One of these action strategies is to invest in home-working spaces by means of renovations and by creating or adapting sufficient physical spaces to drive productivity (Armillei et al., 2021).

Our current research is focusing on UK employees experiences in 2021 employed by medium (up to 250 employees) to large (more than 250 employees) size organisations because these employers have duty of care to ensure that employees are supported while WfH.

In 25 March 2020, Coronavirus Act 2020 got Royal Assent in the UK and from 26 March 2020 lockdown measures legally came into force nationally. 4 July 2020 UK first local lockdown came into force in Leicester and parts of Leicestershire within the East Midland region. This extended lockdown allowed for a natural research project to understand employees experiences while WfH and employed by Leicester-based employers.

The research team identified three major Leicester-based employers: De Montfort University, Leicester City Council, and East Midlands chamber to survey their employees about WfH experiences. We conducted a scoping online survey in 2021 to answer these two research questions:

- 1- What are the best solutions to space design for WfH to enhance well-being and productivity?
- 2- What changes to their home spaces have knowledge workers and public administrators in the East Midlands made to enable WfH during COVID-19 lockdown?

In the next section, we explain the research approach including survey design, participants recruitment, and research analysis. In the key findings and discussion section, we present key themes emerged from the research analysis and linking these to the wider research of WfH literature. Conclusion and next phase of this research are included in the last section.

Approach

Our research aimed to understand the lived employees experiences of WfH during COVID-19 lockdown with focus on knowledge workers and public administrators because the nature of their work are broadly similar. Both employees require digital and office-related infrastructure including adequate desking and furnishing. The core research team was based at De Montfort University and covering these primary disciplines: architecture, interior design, and applied psychology. The core team combined these disciplines and designed online survey including both quantitative and qualitative questions.

Survey design

The survey consisted of both open-ended and Likert scale questions. In the first part of the survey, participants were asked if they had experience in WfH prior to the COVID-19 lockdown restrictions, and if so, how frequently they did so. These responses were recorded

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through Likert questionnaires. They were also asked about their households, for example, how many people they shared their home environment with, and their occupations.

In the second part of the survey, participants were asked about the quality of their home working environments. Firstly, using open-ended responses, they were asked to describe their WfH environment, highlighting what they like, dislike, and prioritise during home working. Secondly, using a Likert scale, they were asked to self-report how comfortable, and stressed they felt while WfH, forming a measure of their subjective well-being. To measure their productivity during WfH, they were asked to estimate how many productive hours they spent WfH.

Research participants

Participants were recruited through a combination of purposive and convenient sampling. The survey was sent out through three major Leicester-based employers in 2021 including: De Montfort University staff, and the employees and members of both Leicester City Council and East Midlands Chamber. The initial sample contained 100 participants with a total of 98 valid responses who were employed as either knowledge workers or public administrators.

Research analysis

We analysed the online survey using these methods: descriptive analysis, conceptual content analysis, and correlation analysis.

Key findings and discussions

Participants profile

The data of 98 participants were suitable for analysis. Most participants in the study were between 46 and 55 years old, with the sample ranging in age between 18 and 75.

In terms of occupation, most respondents were lecturers 30.6% (N=30), falling into the 46-55 age category. Of these 98 participants, 65.3% (N = 64) reported that they had previously worked from home prior to the COVID-19 lockdown restrictions, with most participants reporting that they previously worked from home at least 1-2 days a week (40.6%). For their home environment, 74.5% (N=73) of participants reported that they had a dedicated space at home to work. These findings are consistent with these employers because WfH can be facilitated in these types of occupations where there is some degree of self-management of work duties.

1. What are the best solutions to space design for WfH to promote well-being and productivity?

To investigate the best space design for home working, participants comfort scores were ordered in descending order, to group those who felt the most comfortable WfH. Then, frequencies of their responses to their WfH priorities, what they liked about their home working environment, and the key features of their home working environment were calculated. Table 1 shows the ten most frequent characteristics found across the three categories.

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Table 1. Frequencies of home working environment characteristics based on high comfort ratings when WfH

Priorities	Frequency	Percent	Likes	Frequency	Percent	Home working space	Frequency	Percent
“good”	13	5.8%	“comfortable”	5	2.79%	“desk”	10	7.04%
“space”	8	3.57%	“work”	5	2.79%	“office”	8	5.63%
“lighting”	7	3.13%	“quiet”	4	2.23%	“room”	7	4.93%
“desk”	7	3.13%	“space”	4	2.23%	“home”	5	3.52%
“quiet”	6	2.68%	“without”	3	1.68%	“spare”	4	2.82%
“chair”	6	2.68%	“time”	3	1.68%	“chair”	4	2.82%
“internet”	5	2.23%	“window”	3	1.68%	“work”	4	2.82%
“work”	4	1.79%	“family”	3	1.68%	“dining”	4	2.82%
“comfortable”	4	1.79%	“home”	3	1.68%	“study”	3	2.11%
“room”	4	1.79%	“plants”	3	1.68%	“table”	3	2.11%

As in Table 1 above, the data also shows three common features which are both priorities and frequently present in the respondents’ home working spaces, “desk,” “room,” and “chair.” This indicates that, to promote comfort when WfH, an adequate room or space set up with a desk and chair are required. As these participants self-reported their comfort scores as the maximum option (10/10), these features are imperative to WfH comfort.

To investigate the best space design for home working, participants self-reported productive hours were ordered descending order, to group those who achieved the most productive time spent WfH. Then, frequencies of their responses to their WfH priorities, what they liked about their home working environment, and their home working environment were calculated. Table 2 shows the ten most frequent characteristics found across the three categories.

Table 2. Frequencies of home working environment characteristics based on high productive hours when WfH

Priorities	Frequency	Percent	Likes	Frequency	Percent	Home working space	Frequency	Percent
“good”	20	5.33%	“work”	14	3.06%	“room”	16	5.82%
“space”	17	4.53%	“space”	13	2.84%	“desk”	14	5.09%
“light”	14	3.73%	“light”	10	2.18%	“office”	14	5.09%
“chair”	13	3.47%	“comfortable”	9	1.97%	“chair”	11	4%
“desk”	12	3.20%	“quiet”	7	1.53%	“dining”	10	3.64%
“comfortable”	11	2.93%	“time”	6	1.31%	“table”	10	3.64%
“internet”	9	2.40%	“desk”	5	1.09%	“spare”	8	2.91%
“quiet”	8	2.13%	“office”	5	1.09%	“study”	7	2.55%
“warmth”	7	1.87%	“view”	4	0.87%	“work”	7	2.55%
“work”	6	1.60%	“garden”	4	0.87%	“home”	7	2.55%

As in Table 2 above, the data presents two main characteristics of home working environments that support productivity, one of which resembling a priority and what they liked of home working environment. Participants frequently stated that a “desk” and “office” were prioritised and liked in their home working environments. As these characteristics were selected based on high productive hours (8+ hours), this indicates that to benefit from productive hours when WfH, individuals would consider organising their space to include a desk and prioritise an office setting.

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Conceptual content analysis

Conceptual content analysis is about selecting concepts to study and then quantify and count their presence in textual data through explicit terms and words.

Participant responses were collected based on the criteria of (a) participants scoring below four on the question related to stress, and (b) participants who achieved over 8 hours of working a day during the COVID-19 restrictions. Data were collected from participants responses to what they liked about their home working environment, and what they prioritised when WfH. The pre-determined categories, based on previous research in well-being and productivity, under investigation were environmental conditions (Foldspang et al., 2014), furnishing in the work environment (Argus & Pääsuke (2021), and a dedicated workspace (Daffern et al., 2022 and Du et al., 2022).

The three categories consisted of relevant codes as described in Table 3.

Table 3. categories and sub categories coding when WfH

Categories	Total likes (n = 44), % (n)	Total priorities (n = 44), % (n)
Environmental Conditions		
Environmental Control	56.4% (22)	68.3% (28)
Comfortable Environment	23.1% (9)	19.5% (8)
Noise Levels	20.5% (8)	12.2% (5)
Furnishing in the Work Environment		
Suitable Furniture	54.6% (6)	43.3% (13)
Comfort	18.2% (2)	36.7% (11)
Resource Proximity	27.3% (3)	20% (6)
Dedicated Workspace		
Flexibility	25.5% (12)	4.8% (3)
Suitable and designated environment	31.9% (15)	11.3% (7)
Adequate Space	10.6% (5)	29% (18)
Technology	12.8% (6)	40.3% (25)
Work-Life Balance	19.2% (9)	14.5% (9)

As in Table 3 above, ‘environmental conditions’ consisted of the codes: environmental control, signalling participants’ ability to adjust their lighting or heat levels to their liking, comfort, signalling how comfortable individuals felt, and noise, with 80 evidence/ terms related to these conditions. ‘Furnishing in the work environment’ consisted of the presence of suitable, and comfortable furniture, as well as the proximity of resources in the working environment, with 40 evidence/ terms related to these conditions. ‘Dedicated workspace’ consisted of mentions of adjusting the workspace, suitable environments, adequate space, the presence of technology, and the ability to separate work from home life, with 108 evidence/ terms related to these conditions.

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In terms of environmental conditions, participants prioritised a self-controlled environment more than they reported liking it. Responses detailed the importance of “additional heating sources” (participant 22), and “ventilation” (participant 9). In contrast, concerning a comfortable environment, and noise levels when WfH, participants seemed to like, rather than prioritise, these more. There were greater instances of participants liking comfortable, quiet working spaces, reporting “*it’s comfortable for working long periods of time*” (participant 2), and “*less interruptions than in the office*” (participant 34)

When considering furniture in the home workspace, participants prioritised the proximity of resources in their working environments. They reported that they ensured “*stationary – mouse mats/pens etc*” (participant 16) was “*accessible at all times*” (participant 20). This also included home comforts, such as one participant who ensured “*access to coffee machine*” (participant 23). Participants also prioritised comfort, ensuring that their chairs were “*comfortable*” (participant 2), “*correct posture*” (participant 22), and “*adjustable*” (participant 40). In terms of likes, participants reported preferences for suitable furniture when WfH. They reported likings for “*height and position for everything*” (participant 48), showing the importance of suitable furnishings.

Furthermore, participants’ dedicated workspace contained priorities and likes. They prioritised adequate space and the presence of technology greater than they liked these factors. They reported the importance of “*space to be able to do the job*” (participant 1), “*room to move and spread about*” (participant 4), as well as “*a good internet connection*” (participant 2). Participants liked their suitable home working environments, the maintenance of work-life balance through separating the working environment, and the flexibility of WfH.

2- What changes to their home spaces have knowledge workers and public administrators in the East Midlands made to enable WfH during COVID-19 lockdown?

Participants reported minor changes including re-organising spaces to accommodate some essential furnishing. This was expected because most of those participants 65.3% (N = 64 out of 98) worked from home before the pandemic and their homes included a dedicated working space. Participants who worked from home for the first time focused on essential requirements to perform their work activities with minimum changes to their home spaces.

A Mann-Whitney U test was used to investigate the effect of space adaptations on productive working hours during WfH. The results indicated that there was no significant difference in productive working hours based on whether the individual reorganised or re-purposed their working environment or not, $U = 812.5, p = .321$.

Additionally, a Mann-Whitney U test was used to investigate the influence of space adaptations on comfort ratings, however, the results indicated that space adaptations had no significant impact on self-reported comfort while WfH, $U = 923, p = .447$. This was also the case for self-reported stress ratings, indicating no influence of adaptations to alleviate stress in home workers, $U = 861, p = .217$. As the research was conducted during UK lockdown, stress levels can be related to multiple factors beyond work-related activities.

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Our scoping online survey confirmed existing research in WfH spaces. Existing research categorised three main aspects to enhancing well-being and productivity: environmental conditions (Foldspang et al., 2014), furnishing (Argus & Pääsuke (2021), and a dedicated workspace (Daffern et al., 2022 and Du et al., 2022).

Our findings are also consistent with The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) empirical research. OECD conducted a survey among 3,404 workers from 23 OECD countries including UK on telework for productivity during and after COVID-19. Nearly 70% of workers reported that working from inappropriate home-working spaces was a barrier to productivity and well-being (Criscuolo et al., 2021).

One of the emerging themes was the practical support offered by employers such as ergonomic furniture, screens, and relevant office-based infrastructure. From the participants comments, this practical support was highly endorsed. A logical follow-up research will be to conduct a comprehensive review on medium to large employers on how they support their employees when WfH?

Conclusion and future research

We surveyed knowledge workers and public administrators in 2021 with a total of 98 valid responses recruited through purposive and convenient sampling. The online survey was shared via Leicester -based employers: De Montfort University, Leicester City Council, and East Midlands chamber.

Our findings identified a dedicated workspace as a significant contributor to comfort. Participants prioritised environmental control, comfortable furnishings, and adequate space while WfH. Our recommendation is that employee-centred environments design and solutions will enhance subjective wellbeing and productivity. These WfH environments will need to be customised to fit the nature of work activities.

Not a passing trend, WfH is here to stay. In light of climate change, the likelihood of other pandemics and the increasing demands of employees to have good work-life fit with less commuting time to be able to work, our recommendations are not to be thought of as COVID-19 specific, rather, the future of work and living in resilient, liveable and sustainable cities and communities.

The next phase of this research will focus on creating and testing a comprehensive design guideline for WfH spaces to enhance subjective well-being and productivity. Research approach will be combining architecture, psychology, and visual methods to create employee-centred environments. Our research will target knowledge employees from medium (up to 250 employees) to large (more than 250 employees) employers with explicit policies around smart and flexible working provisions. Those employers have duty of care towards their employees and will be required to enhance well-being and productivity of their employees when WfH.

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